

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF SODIUM SALTS OF AROMATIC ACIDS AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES

Salt	T °C	K _A dm ³ mol ⁻¹	-ΔG°	ΔH°	ΔS°
Gallate	25	5.76 ± 0.53	4.85	2.35	0.023
	35	5.74 ± 1.14	4.48	2.85	0.023
	45	6.65 ± 1.66	5.02	2.35	0.024
Phthalate Mechanism (i)	25	42.40 ± 2.70	9.23	1.67	0.037
	35	44.50 ± 3.10	9.74	1.67	0.038
	45	46.70 ± 3.20	10.20	1.67	0.038
Phthalate Mechanism (ii)	25	682.60 ± 327.20	16.20	2.50	0.063
	35	724.70 ± 350.10	16.90	2.50	0.063
	45	780.10 ± 380.60	17.60	2.50	0.064
Terephthalate Mechanism (i)	25	33.10 ± 1.10	8.70	3.18	0.040
	35	35.90 ± 3.00	9.20	3.18	0.041
	45	39.70 ± 2.60	9.70	3.18	0.041
Terephthalate Mechanism (ii)	25	493.90 ± 291.70	15.40	4.02	0.066
	35	546.20 ± 291.00	16.10	4.02	0.066
	45	621.80 ± 283.50	17.00	4.02	0.067

still small ones. However, the sodium ions are found to be more associated to the phthalate ion than to the terephthalate ion, which is opposite to what one would expect according to the pK_A values¹⁰. This reverse order may be explained on the basis of the inductive effect of the carboxylate group in the *para*-position. In the second case, the K_A values obtained are not acceptable due to the large values of their standard deviations, which exceed 50% in all cases. We, therefore, suggest that only the first association mechanism is acceptable.

Thus only three of the five sodium salts are shown to be associated, namely, Na-gallate, -phthalate and -terephthalate; the other two, namely, Na-*m*-hydroxybenzoate and 3,5-dihydroxybenzoate are completely dissociated.

It is worth noting that the stoichiometric association constants for sodium gallate is comparable to that of the sodium bisulphate^{11,12} ion-pair at the same ionic strength. For example at an ionic strength of 0.21 M at 25°, K_(NaHSO₄) = 3.70 ± 0.3 dm³ mol⁻¹ and K_(Na-gallate) = 3.66 dm³ mol⁻¹. On the other hand, the values for Na-phthalate and -terephthalate are much larger than those of NaHSO₄. Thus, the association of sodium salts of inorganic ligands are comparable to those of organic ligand with the same charge under the same conditions.

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Solute-Solvent Interaction Studies of some Solutions Involving Ascorbic Acid

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Manuscript received 16 June 1979, revised 24 March 1986, accepted 7 June 1986

MULTICOMPONENT solutions play an important role in physiological processes of body fluids and cell equilibria. Ascorbic acid is believed either to promote the secretion of enzymes or create suitable molecular environment for enzymes to act effectively¹. Kaulgud² *et al.* have studied the apparent molar volume, apparent molar compressibility and viscosity of ascorbic acid in water and 0.06 M NaCl at 25°.

The study reported here is a part of the investigations regarding thermodynamic and transport studies of solutions involving ascorbic acid. Some interesting results are expected in the solute-solvent interactions in water and in electrolyte solutions in presence of vitamin C, hence the studies of ascorbic acid in water and different electrolyte solutions at different concentrations were carried out. Properties like molar volume, viscosity and conductance have been studied to interpret the results in terms of solute-solvent interaction in recent past³⁻⁶. In the present communication, results for the studies of viscosity and conductance of solutions consisting of KCl, NaCl and LiCl with ascorbic acid are described.

Experimental

Conductivity water of specific conductance $1.3 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$, was obtained by distilling it thrice over alkaline potassium permanganate. KCl and NaCl (AnalaR) were used without further purification. LiCl (B.D.H.) was purified by crystallising from water, dried for 24 h at 130°, in an oven, and then kept over P₂O₅ in vacuum desiccator before use. Ascorbic acid (AnalaR) was recrystallised from a mixture of methanol-ethyl ether-petroleum ether, dried and kept over anhydrous CaCl₂ in a desiccator.

NOTES

All solutions were made by weight, and conversion of molality into molarity was carried out by using the proper expression⁷. The viscosity⁸, density⁹, and conductance¹⁰ measurements were carried out by methods described in our earlier publications. All measurements were made in a thermostat ($\pm 0.05^\circ$). The standard deviation in viscosity, density and conductance measurements are ± 0.02 mp, $\pm 0.000 011$ g cm⁻³ and ± 0.04 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹, respectively.

Results and Discussion

The equivalent conductance and viscosity values of ascorbic acid in different aqueous solutions of LiCl, KCl and NaCl are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

The plots of Δ vs $\sqrt{C}$ in all the solutions studied, containing ascorbic acid, are curved. The proof that association takes place, is revealed from the plot of $\log \Delta$ vs $\log C$, drawn according to the theory of Fuoss and Krauss¹¹. The values of slope (close to -0.5) show that partial association takes place¹². The values of Δ_0 (limiting equivalent conductance) were calculated from Owen's

TABLE 2—VISCOSITY OF SOLUTIONS (MILLIPOISE) INVOLVING ASCORBIC ACIDS

Solvent system	$C \times 10^3$ (mol cm ⁻³)	η_s mp
Water $\eta_0 = 7.23$ mp	9.855	7.34
	19.507	7.57
	24.217	7.76
	28.927	7.88
	33.604	7.97
0.01 M LiCl (aq.) $\eta_0 = 6.79$ mp	38.243	8.17
	2.483	7.06
	4.953	7.11
	9.853	7.28
	19.502	7.50
0.01 M NaCl (aq.) $\eta_0 = 6.99$ mp	29.150	7.86
	38.227	8.11
	2.484	7.09
	4.954	7.17
	9.855	7.25
0.01 M KCl (aq.) $\eta_0 = 7.16$ mp	19.504	7.52
	28.974	7.77
	38.270	8.04
	4.953	7.22
	9.856	7.33
	19.507	7.61
	28.964	7.92
	38.258	8.25

TABLE 1—EQUIVALENT CONDUCTANCE OF SOLUTIONS INVOLVING ASCORBIC ACID

Solvent system	$C \times 10^3$ (mol cm ⁻³)	Λ Ω^{-1} cm ² mol ⁻¹
Water 1.9×10^{-9} Ω^{-1} cm ⁻¹	0.993	65.65
	2.983	43.41
	3.977	34.15
	5.968	30.40
	7.960	28.79
0.001 M LiCl (aq.) 0.685×10^{-4} Ω^{-1} cm ⁻¹	9.955	30.74
	0.995	62.54
	2.982	43.26
	3.979	39.13
	5.969	30.66
0.001 M NaCl 1.121×10^{-4} Ω^{-1} cm ⁻¹	7.962	32.33
	9.954	31.49
	0.596	68.79
	0.993	60.62
	3.978	39.35
0.001 M KCl (aq.) 1.744×10^{-4} Ω^{-1} cm ⁻¹	5.969	31.30
	7.962	35.51
	0.595	84.01
	0.994	74.13
	1.990	66.73
	2.986	44.21
	4.977	35.86
	5.974	32.37

plots¹³, the approximate value of Δ_0 being taken from Δ vs $\sqrt{C}$ plots. The order of magnitude of Δ_0 for ascorbic acid in electrolyte solutions is, KCl > NaCl > LiCl. The dissociation constant and slope ($d \log \Delta / d \log C$) indicate the reverse order. Though in KCl the association is more, yet it is not complete. The unassociated K⁺ ions have higher mobility than Na⁺ and Li⁺ ions¹⁴. Thus higher Δ_0 of ascorbic acid in KCl is not unexpected.

The viscosity data were analysed with the help of Jone-Dole equation¹⁵. The values of the parameters A and B of Jone-Dole equation are determined from the intercept and the slope of the linear plots of $[(\eta_s/\eta_0) - 1] / \sqrt{C}$ vs $\sqrt{C}$. Zero A values and positive B values are obtained in the present study. This suggests that ascorbic acid behaves as structure promoter¹⁶ in water as well as in other electrolyte solutions. The value of B for KCl is considerably high suggesting more ion-association or triple-ion formation, as is also indicated from conductance studies. Table 3 shows values of Δ_0 , dissociation constant, slope of plots $\log \Delta$ vs $\log$

TABLE 3

Sl. no.	Solvent	Δ_0 Ω^{-1} cm ² mol ⁻¹	Slope ($d \log \Delta / d \log C$)	Dissociation constant $K \times 10^4$	B mol ⁻¹ cm ³	A mol ⁻¹ cm ^{3/2}
1.	Water	89.3	-0.37	4.22	+0.49	0.0
2.	0.001 M LiCl (aq.)	90.7	-0.38	4.21	—	—
3.	0.001 M NaCl (aq.)	92.9	-0.40	3.69	—	—
4.	0.001 M KCl (aq.)	108.8	-0.48	3.06	—	—
5.	0.01 M LiCl (aq.)	—	—	—	+0.42	0.0
6.	0.01 M NaCl (aq.)	—	—	—	+0.38	0.0
7.	0.01 M KCl (aq.)	—	—	—	+0.60	0.0

C and A and B parameters of Jone-Dole equation, of different solutions involving ascorbic acid.

analysis and infrared spectra. The following α,β -unsaturated ketones were synthesised :

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(I)

- 1 ; R = C₆H₄CH₃-p, R₁ = OH, R₂ = CH₂C₆H₅, R₃ = CH₂CH₂CN
- 2 ; R = C₆H₄OCH₃-p, R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = CH₂C₆H₅, R₃ = OH, CH₂CN
- 3 ; R = C₆H₄Br-p, R₁ = OH, R₂ = OH, C₆H₅, R₃ = CH₂CH₂CN
- 4 ; R = C₆H₄Cl-p, R₁ = OH, R₂ = CH₂C₆H₅, R₃ = CH₂CH₂CN
- 5 ; R = OH(CH₂)₃, R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = CH₂C₆H₅, R₃ = CH₂CH₂CN
- 6 ; R = C₆H₁₁, R₁ = OH, R₂ = CH₂C₆H₅, R₃ = OH, CH₂CN
- 7 ; R = C₆H₅, R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = OH, C₆H₅, R₃ = OH, CH₂CN
- 8 ; R = C₆H₄NO₂-m, R₁ = H, R₂ = CH₂C₆H₅, R₃ = CH₂CH₂CN
- 9 ; R = C₆H₅, R₁ = H, R₂ = CH₂C₆H₅, R₃ = CH₂CH₂CN
- 10 ; R = C₆H₄OCH₃-m, R₁ = H, R₂ = CH₂C₆H₅, R₃ = OH, CH₂CN
- 11 ; R = C₆H₄CH₃-p, R₁ = H, R₂ = CH₂C₆H₅, R₃ = CH₂CH₂CN
- 12 ; R = C₆H₄CH₃-p, R₁ = H, R₂ = R₃ = C₂H₅
- 13 ; R = C₆H₅, R₁ = H, R₂ = R₃ = C₂H₅
- 14 ; R = OH(CH₂)₃, R₁ = H, R₂ = R₃ = C₂H₅

(II)

- 15 ; R = C₆H₄OCH₃-p, R₁ = NO₂
- 16 ; R = C₆H₄OCH₃-p, R₁ = Br
- 17 ; R = C₆H₄Cl-p, R₁ = Br
- 18 ; R = C₆H₅, R₁ = Br
- 19 ; R = C₆H₄Br-p, R₁ = Br
- 20 ; R = C₆H₄OCH₃-p, R₁ = H

Synthesis of some α,β -Unsaturated-ketones.

Part-I

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Manuscript received 4 August 1981, accepted 24 December 1985

VARIOUS α,β -unsaturated ketones have been synthesised by Claisen reaction¹, which may be useful as insect-attractants and possess antifungal activity.

Some ketones like anisylacetone² and benzyl acetone³ etc., have been found to be useful as insect-attractants and possess antifungal activity as well. With this aim in view, a number of α,β -unsaturated ketones have been synthesised by Claisen reaction. The synthesis of such ketones (1 and 2) was carried out by condensing aromatic aldehydes with aliphatic or aromatic ketones in presence of 5% ethanolic alkali followed by continuous stirring with a mechanical stirrer. The ketones, so separated, were purified and characterised by elemental

Experimental

All the α,β -unsaturated ketones (1-20) were synthesised by treating one mole each of the corresponding aromatic aldehydes with aliphatic or aromatic ketones in 5% ethanolic sodium hydroxide, and stirring for 3 h. The solids were separated by filtration and crystallised from alcohol; while liquids were extracted with ether, washed with water, solvent distilled off, the residue so obtained was a thin syrupy liquid, which could not be distilled even under reduced pressure in each case. The solids were characterised by their m.ps., elemental analyses, infrared spectra and preparation of 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazones, while liquids were characterised by the preparation of 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazones, elemental analyses and infrared spectra of the latter.

All the data are given in Table 1.

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